

Solution Stability Constant of Copper (II) Mandelate Complex

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Recently Khadikar and Bhatia¹ and Smith² have reported the formation of 1 : 1 complex between Cu(II) and mandelic acid at 25° and 0.058 *M* (KCl) ionic strength on the basis of conductometric and glass electrode methods. We observed that in addition to 1 : 1 complex, copper also forms the 1 : 2 complex with mandelic acid. In the present communication the stepwise stabilities of copper (II) mandelate complexes in solution have been determined using Bjerrum's method³. The titration medium has been maintained at a constant ionic strength (0.1 *M* NaClO₄) and at a temperature 30±0.2°.

In calculating \bar{n} and [A⁻], the concentrations were corrected for changes in volume produced by the addition of alkali during titrations. In this way, a series of values for \bar{n} and [A⁻] corresponding to different values of *pH*, were obtained (Table I). The formation curve was obtained by plotting \bar{n} values against *pA* (Figure 1).

TABLE I

<i>pH</i>	\bar{n}	<i>Solution Stability Constant</i>				
		<i>V_t</i>	[H ⁺] × 10 ³	[HA] × 10 ³	[A ⁻] × 10 ³	<i>pA</i>
2.50	0.10	50.2 ml	3.160	7.97	0.978	3.009
2.55	0.20	50.7	2.818	7.88	1.088	2.963
2.60	0.40	51.3	2.510	7.80	1.230	2.910
2.70	0.80	52.0	1.995	7.69	1.540	2.812
2.80	1.12	53.2	1.585	7.52	1.910	2.721
3.00	1.60	55.2	1.000	7.24	2.900	2.537
3.20	1.85	55.7	0.631	7.18	4.421	2.386
3.30	2.00	56.6	0.501	7.07	5.470	2.262
3.40	2.12	57.8	0.398	6.92	6.750	2.171
3.50	2.22	58.8	0.316	6.81	8.351	2.072

The values of log *K*₁, log *K*₂, log *K*_{av} and log β₂ work out to be 2.85, 2.56, 2.71 and 5.41 respectively.

1. P. V. Khadikar and R. L. Bhatia, M.Sc. Thesis, Vikram Univ. (1967).
2. I. C. Smith, Diss., Kansas State Univ., (1961).
3. J. Bjerrum. 'Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution'. P. Hass and Sons, Copenhagen, (1941).

FIGURE 1
COPPER (II) - MANDELATE

Fig. 1

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